

Mobile Operating System Verification Layer for Preventing Spoofed Mobile Application Installation

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Abstract— Mobile application spoofing is a serious problem that enterprise sectors have a tough time combating. Applications can have an identical package name as the application that the enterprise user is attempting to install, which in theory would bypass enterprise security. This paper focuses on apps spoofing enterprise level apps. The security company Lookout recently researched malware that was impersonating apps such as “Cisco’s Business Class Email app, ADP, Dropbox, FedEx Mobile, Zendesk, VMWare’s Horizon Client, Blackboard’s Mobile Learn app, and others [4].” The malware will “spoof the app’s legitimate package name, either using the same package name or one very similar [4].” Employees using these apps are more likely to “award permissions to apps pretending to be those trusted brands, and less likely to uninstall them [4].” This is troublesome especially when “67% of IT and security pros say that their organization has likely already been hit by an attack through mobile [4].” In this paper, I proposed having a verification layer that guards against spoofed applications that are downloaded through third-party vendors.

Keywords—*android security, android spoofing, mobile operating system security, mobile app spoofing, mobile application spoofing.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile devices are a necessity in the United States and the world. Ninety-six percent of the US population owns a mobile phone, with 81% of those phones being smart phones [1]. Aside from phones, about half of the population also owns other forms of devices running a mobile operating system, such as android and iOS tablets [1]. Worldwide, there are 2.71 billion users today, meaning that roughly 35% of the entire global population has a device that might be compromised in the future, if not already; that number increases to 5.13 billion, or 66% of the population, when talking about mobile devices in general [2]. The potential to compromise a mobile device increases exponentially when the device is connected to a network: there are 8.9 billion mobile connections [2].

There are numerous types of mobile device weaknesses with mobile applications serving as attack vectors most of the time [3]. Some common ones include bad data storage practices, malware, unauthorized access, lack of encryption, and data leaks from syncing [3]. This paper focuses on apps spoofing enterprise level applications. The security company Lookout recently researched malware that was impersonating apps such as “Cisco’s Business Class Email app, ADP, Dropbox, FedEx Mobile, Zendesk, VMWare’s Horizon Client, Blackboard’s Mobile Learn app, and others [4].” The malware will “spoof the app’s legitimate package name, either using the same package name or one very similar [4].” Employees using these apps are more likely to “award permissions to apps pretending to be those trusted brands, and less likely to uninstall them [4].” This is troublesome especially when “67% of IT and security pros say that their organization has likely already been hit by an attack through mobile [4].”

II. CURRENT RESEARCH

Most mobile device spoofing research focuses on network spoofing detection and mobile device access spoofing prevention, such as facial recognition spoofing detection. One solution to combating spoofing attacks was proposed by Luka Malisa, Kari Kostianinen and Srdjan Capkun. Their focus was on the login screen but could be expanded to the entire application itself. Their spoofing detection approach “tailored to the protection of mobile app login screens, using screenshot extraction and visual similarity comparisons [5].” They used “deception rate as a novel similarity metric for measuring how likely the user is to consider a potential spoofing app as one of the protected applications [5].”

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

My proposed solution is to integrate a verification layer into each mobile device. This will require the participation from both the user’s mobile device, the enterprise itself, and a governing body. The enterprise will provide a verification domain to the governing body to which the mobile operating system can submit a request to. The governing body will store the domains for each enterprise level app that wants to participate. The following steps will occur when the user wants to download an application outside of the mobile device’s official app store; this procedure will work for applications with the same package name:

1. The user clicks on the download link.
2. The enterprise app generates a unique key and stores it in a database within its own organization.
3. The key is also integrated into the application itself and is downloaded to the user’s phone.
4. Prior to installing the app, the verification layer contacts the governing body and requests for the domain to which the downloaded key will be submitted to; it does so by submitting the application’s package name to the governing body.
5. The governing body returns the domain to the mobile device.
6. The verification layer on the mobile device submits the key to the provided domain.
7. The enterprise checks the submitted key and notifies the verification layer whether the key exists inside its database.
8. The key is deleted from the enterprise database.
9. The verification layer receives the notification that the key exists, and it allows the mobile device to proceed with the app installation process.

2. Enterprise generates key

Fig. 1. Shows the process of installing an enterprise level application where the governing body stores the domain that points to the enterprise database from which the key can be verified.

Another possibility would be to have the key stored inside the governing body's database. That way, the application would receive a key and submit it to the governing body directly. The governing body would store the key temporarily and return the verification details directly.

If the package name is not found inside the governing body, similar verified applications would be returned to the

user. The verifier would display a warning message stating that the application attempting to install might be compromised, and the user would be provided with other official options. If no other options are available, the user would be provided with a warning message that states that the application might be trying to mimic other applications; it would be up to the user to allow the app to be installed.

Fig. 2. Shows the enterprise mobile application install procedure where the governing body stores the key

IV. ADVANTAGES

The main advantage of the proposed solution is that it virtually eliminates the capability of spoofing a mobile application with the identical package name. If all mobile applications adopted the verifier method, the necessity for mobile antimalware protection would virtually be eliminated. The application process would be stricter since the governing body would have to verify each mobile application and make sure that the new application does not have malicious intent. Applications would also only be downloaded from authorized vendors due to the key generation process.

V. DISADVANTAGES

This type of protection only works for applications that participate in this type of verification process. Other apps might still be installed on the device that compromise the user's device. Another disadvantage is the cost of creating such a verification system. Each mobile operating system would need to receive an update with the verifier layer

integrated into its operating system. Lastly, the governing body would also have to be created.

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